

An Imminent Revolution

“The present book expounds the multifaceted nature of blockchain technology and its tamper-proof ecosystem for conducting real-world activities such as education, healthcare, real estate, transport, banking, business, supply chain management, e-commerce, decentralized finance. The readers will discover the potential use of blockchain technology in all significant walks of life and learn to handle transactional procedures. The narrative is lucid, with great art-work, and is sure to enthuse readers. With its simple handling of a complex subject, this book is a treasure for every scholar and entrepreneur”.

Indraneel Shankar Dani, Former Addl. Chief Secretary, MP, India.

We are in the midst of another big revolution called BLOCKCHAIN, a distributed database that maintains an ever-growing list of records, called blocks. This innovation landscape represents only 12 years of work by an elite group of geeks, cryptographers and mathematicians.

In times to come, blockchain will permeate every human pursuit, making processes efficient and smart. As the full potential of these breakthroughs is realized in society, things will gradually begin to happen differently – international money transfers will be faster and more reliable; verification will be easy; identity will be global, decentralized; and no person - whether administrator, manager, industrialist, start-up, employer, service provider, educationist, student or user, will remain untouched. Obviously, the world will need to embrace this technology with open arms.

In view of this, the author strongly believes that every section of the society should be made aware of blockchain, be it a budding technologist, a start-up enthusiast or a non-technical user of decentralized apps. This article provides an in-depth understanding on the blockchain ecosystem, architecture, Ethereum, Hyperledger and cryptocurrencies, followed by a comprehensive discussion on potential uses of blockchain such as cryptography, cyber-security, identity management, credential verification, job certification, healthcare, remote health monitoring, organ transplantation, genomics, pharmaceutical supply chain, food and civil supplies, etc. Live screen-shots and associated code-cells, provided in between the text, will help the readers to comprehend banking, business, decentralized finance, prediction market, portfolio management, quadratic funding, crowd funding, e-commerce etc. with a de novo approach.

The content provides a practical step-wise mechanism for each reader to implement their own content-based storage system. Our approach is to help you operate this revolutionary technology by introducing you to its every detail. With this new technology under your control, you will be able to access the features of blockchain as easily as operating a simple mobile app. So, join the blockchain revolution, learn how to develop decentralized applications, and get ahead of your peers.

Blockchain for Real World Applications

Rishabh Garg | BITS India | Founder & CEO, Scholars Park
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Blockchain: An Imminent Revolution

Book-keeping has been a cornerstone of civilization since the Babylonian era because the exchange of value required two strangers to trust each other's accounts. We still need an integrated system that can record all our transactions, keep the society organized and maintain public trust [**Garg, 2023**] *Blockchain for Real World Applications - Rishabh Garg. John Wiley & Sons, Inc. US, 01-388: ISBN - 9781119903734*.

The technical architecture and protocols of **Distributed Ledger Technology** (DLT) allow the simultaneous access, verification and irreversible updating of data over a network spanning multiple nodes or locations. Blockchain is one of its many forms such as **DAG**, **Hashgraph**, **Holochain** and **Tempo** (Radix). Blockchain is an imminent revolution and an entirely new app development protocol. Like the Internet a quarter century ago, blockchain applications may permeate our daily lives in the coming years [**Garg, 2022**].

Blockchain is essentially a digital ledger that tracks transactions. Transactions can denote anything – cash, digital currencies, stocks or any other asset. Blockchain is able to satisfy a wide range of terms and conditions for acquiring or settling these assets through so-called smart contracts.

The way in which transactions are recorded on multiple computers within a decentralized network differentiates the blockchain from the simple ledger. Once a consensus is reached, each node on the network updates its own copy of the ledger all together. In the absence of consensus, the rest of the network instantly stops attempting to add or remove a node.

The blockchain uses triple-entry accounting, where one entry is made on the credit side, the other on the debit side, and the third on the immutable shared ledger – managed by advanced mathematical algorithms and impervious cryptography. Read more - *Blockchain for Real World Applications - Rishabh Garg. John Wiley & Sons, Inc. US, 01-388: ISBN - 9781119903734*.

Blockchain is a series of blocks that form a comprehensive list of transactions that are transmitted and replicated across the network as a digital public ledger. Blockchain ecosystem consists of **nodes** – users or computers – that maintain a complete copy of the record or ledger, whereas **blocks** are data formats that are used to store records of transactions and transmit them among all nodes in the network [**Garg, 2021**].

Stuart Haber and W Scott Stornetta [1991] were the first to introduce the concept of blockchain. But Satoshi Nakamoto, the person behind the pseudonym, popularized it in 2008 so that it could serve as a public log of bitcoin transactions. Programmable smart contracts, constitutional design and blockchain consensus protocol have been core areas of innovation during the past decade and a half.

BLOCKCHAIN TIMELINE

Over the past 15 years, there has been much innovation in blockchain consensus technologies, programmable smart contracts, and fiduciary architecture.

BLOCKCHAIN 1.0

Blockchain 1.0 was used as a digital currency for large scale trading, small value transactions, forex, gaming and money laundering. There are many benefits to employing blockchain technology for digital currency, but its fundamental advantage is that it provides a safe and secure platform for asset transfers without the need for intermediaries or counterparties. More than 4500 different varieties of cryptocurrencies are now available. The most popular are Bitcoin (2009), Litecoin (2011), Namecoin (2011), Dogecoin (2013), and Peercoin, with a total market capitalization of US\$ 295 billion (2012).

BLOCKCHAIN 2.0

The expansion of Blockchain 2.0 applications enabled smart-contracts, decentralized applications (dApps) and decentralized autonomous organizations (DAOs). It played a pivotal role in specific areas of finance – banking, stock trading, credit systems, supply chain finance, payment clearing, anti-counterfeiting, mutual insurance, and disrupting traditional currencies and payment methods. It facilitated the implementation of smart contracts using some programmable contract languages, including Ethereum, Codius, and Hyperledger.

BLOCKCHAIN 3.0

In addition to currency and finance, Blockchain 3.0 has been able to establish dominance in areas such as education, health, science, transportation and logistics. It involves a more sophisticated type of smart contract to create a decentralized organizational unit that creates its own rules and provides substantial autonomy.

BLOCKCHAIN 4.0

Blockchain 4.0 is evolving into a business-friendly ecosystem for the masses. It is a fusion of blockchain with the most comprehensive options of the future cutting-edge technologies such as Internet of Things, cloud computing, artificial intelligence and robotics. By examining the potential of virtual blockchains within a single blockchain, the system can earn unrestrained scalability. Blockchain 4.0 refers to ideas and solutions that rationalize technology for business needs, especially Industry 4.0 and commerce. Blockchain technology can be used to improve a variety of processes including supply chain management, corporate workflow, financial transactions, IoT data collection, health monitoring, asset management and credit systems.

Thus, blockchain 4.0 promises a digital architecture that combines automation, accountability, and privacy protection to generate a frictionless experience in the real world [**Garg, 2021; 2023**].

BLOCKCHAIN ARCHITECTURE

Blockchain verifies the validity of transactions through an asymmetric cryptography technique. Here a mathematical process known as **hash function** is used to convert any data into a string of alphanumeric values. It is a process called **encryption** that scrambles the readable text which can only be read by the person who has the secret code or decryption key. There are two main forms of encryption – **asymmetric encryption** (public key) and **symmetric encryption**. Symmetric encryption has only one private (secret) key, and is used by all communicating parties for both encryption and decryption.

Here the field hash and encrypted transaction data acts as a digital signature. The original copy of the data and a secure hash of the data are sent to the recipient. The recipient calculates a new hash using the original data obtained after decrypting the secure hash. If both are the same, it means that the received data has not been changed.

DECENTRALIZED IDENTIFIER

Decentralized IDs enable peer-to-peer connections between two parties that are globally unique, tenacious and pseudo-anonymous. DIDs provide identity-owner control and sovereignty over identities because they are not dependent on centralized registries, authorities, or identity suppliers. Since a person can have multiple DIDs, it is more difficult to monitor them in all their activities. Read more - [*Blockchain for Real World Applications - Rishabh Garg. John Wiley & Sons, Inc. US, 01-388: ISBN - 9781119903734.*](#)

BLOCKCHAIN ECOSYSTEM

A blockchain ecosystem is a network of users sharing nodes for common business activity and purpose. Each blockchain block contains about 1 MB of data. When the 1 MB data capacity of the first block is filled, the information is stored chronologically in this block before being repeated in the second block [**Garg, 2021**].

Each block receives a different hash that exactly matches the string of data in that block to tie all these blocks together in a sequence. A block receives a new hash if even there is a minor change within it. The system relies on decentralized databases to control the emergence of data between entities via a P2P (peer-to-peer) network, where consensus methods ensure replication across nodes of the network.

The individual nodes make up a blockchain ecosystem, and each has its own copy of the ledger. Nodes communicate with each other to agree on a ledger record, eliminating the need for a central authority or any third party to coordinate or verify. In addition to the transmission and verification of supplied data on the blockchain, nodes also assist in the entry of new data. The act of recording transactions on a new block and adding them to an existing chain is called **mining** and it occurs when all nodes reach a consensus. In a blockchain, each block has its own nonce and hash, which is preceded by the hash of the block in the chain.

A cryptographic hash function generates a hash in a blockchain, which turns each input string into an output string with 64 digits. Not all hashes are valid. The hash of a block must start with at least ten consecutive zeros to be qualified on the blockchain. Each block receives a **nonce**, which is a small amount of unique data. Miners have to continuously engage in mining, which is the process of constantly modifying and hashing the block's data in search of a workable hash. In order to find a valid signature (output), miners have to constantly change the block structure (nonce) and use a lot of electricity. The more computational power they do have, the faster they process the various block compositions to find a good hash.

PUBLIC AND PRIVATE BLOCKCHAIN

There are three main types of blockchains: public, private, and consortium blockchains. Any user who wishes to engage in network transactions can do so on a **public blockchain**, with no restrictions. On the other hand, on **private blockchains**, only nodes from a particular organization can participate in the consensus process. Hence, it is also known as permissioned blockchain. **Consortium blockchain** is a semi-private network of like-minded businesses to increase productivity, accountability and transparency.

BLOCKCHAIN CONSENSUS

In order to reach consensus on the state of the blockchain and ensure the validity of transactions, a fault-tolerant mechanism is employed, and is called the **consensus mechanism**. In this, the current state of the distributed ledger is agreed upon by each member of the blockchain network. To add a new block to the chain, a node has to accomplish a computing task, known as **Proof-of-Work**. PoW is a form of consensus that the bitcoin network employs. A lot of energy is wasted in these operations because PoW requires miners to perform enormous computations. **Proof-of-Stake** is a less energy-intensive alternative to PoW that requires miners to prove that they are the legitimate owners of the currency. This is based on a illogical premise that users with more

currency are less likely to attack the network. Several consensus algorithms have been proposed to overcome this impasse, including **PBFT, DPoS, Peercoin, Ripple, Tendermint**, etc.

In order to ensure effectiveness, safety, and convenience, some workers have proposed the greedy heavy-observation subtree (**GHOST**) chain selection rule. In this system, branches are weighed by GHOST so that miners can choose the best branch to follow, rather than the longest branch plan [Simpolinski and Zohar, 2013].

PAYMENT VERIFICATION IN BLOCKCHAIN

There are two possible types of payment verifications: Simple payment verification and Full payment verification.

As part of the **Simple Payment Verification** (SPV) process, a thin or lightweight client can download the block header, which is much lighter than the entire block. It is easier and more useful for the user to save only one copy of the block header from the longest proof-of-work chain and obtain the Merkle branch linking the transaction to the block. Verification is reliable as long as honest nodes are in control of the network. But the moment an attacker takes control of the network, the system gets exposed.

In contrast, **Full payment verification** requires a thick or heavy wallet, which is a complete copy of the blockchain. These wallet programs validate and relay other people's trades in addition to managing the user's own transactions. In order to provide personalized results and choose the blockchain with the highest proof of work, all parties (all nodes) on the network need to be connected. Thus, depending on connectivity, it can take several days for a blockchain network to be downloaded using the bitcoin wallet application. Read more - [Blockchain for Real World Applications - Rishabh Garg, John Wiley & Sons, Inc. US, 01-388: ISBN - 9781119903734](#).

CRYPTOCURRENCIES

Cryptocurrencies, such as Bitcoin, Ether, or Litecoin, are digital tokens that are traded on a blockchain and are used to make purchases of products and services. Blockchain technology is used by cryptocurrencies to complement the benefits of a public ledger and a sophisticated cryptographic security system. Over the years, these currencies have become incredibly popular, leading to the existence of more than 18,000 cryptocurrencies worldwide with a market worth of \$3.2 trillion. A bitcoin is currently worth 3,120,210.68 INR.

SCRIPTS

Scripts are considered one of the fundamental considerations in the implementation of the business logic layer on the blockchain. Simply put, bitcoin transactions are information that reflects the movement of bitcoins from one wallet to another. Usually the first transaction in a new block creates new currency but never spends them. In these transactions the input is left blank and such an empty input is called a **Coinbase transaction**. The reward created by this transaction can also be distributed to one or more wallet addresses like a typical bitcoin

transaction. After a specific number of successful blocks are contributed, the reward is halved for each successful block added to the blockchain, maintaining bitcoin as a finite supply, inflation-resistant resource.

Since Bitcoin is not a form of government-issued legal tender, its popularity has created new avenues for it to be exchanged for fiat money, such as cryptocurrency exchanges, bitcoin debit cards, bitcoin ATMs, Metal Pay and peer-to-peer network.

Initially the peer-to-peer cryptocurrency known as Bitcoin was used for regular transactions but Bitcoin changed over time from a penny to an investment vehicle as it gained popularity and increased in value.

It was believed that the blockchain technology on which it operated lacked scalability since it was intrinsically unable to manage high volumes of transactions. Thus, in August 2017, the original cryptocurrency Bitcoin split into two distinct cryptocurrencies, **Bitcoin Cash** and **Bitcoin SV**. In November 2018, the cryptocurrency experienced another fork, dividing into **Bitcoin Cash ABC** and **Bitcoin Cash SV (Satoshi Vision)**. Because it makes use of the original Bitcoin Cash client, Bitcoin Cash ABC is now referred to as Bitcoin Cash.

Developers can use smart contract languages such as CashScript to enable more complex operations using Bitcoin Cash than with Bitcoin. Bitcoin Cash can be a hard asset, such as real estate, gold, or other physical goods, as Bitcoin has a hard cap of 21 million coins, allowing users to retain value in digital form for a very long time.

ETHEREUM

Ethereum is a variant of blockchain created by Russian-Canadian programmer Vitalik Buterin and his colleagues. Ethereum is a decentralized blockchain platform that was built with a shared global infrastructure. Each node in the network runs an operating system – the Ethereum Virtual Machine, which has the ability to understand and run programs known as smart contracts. Thus, Ethereum reinforces the benefits of the bitcoin blockchain by enabling programmers to write code that emulates the fundamental functionality of a decentralized app or dApp.

SMART CONTRACTS

Smart contract is an application code stored at a specific address (contract address) on the blockchain. Applications can implement the operation of smart contracts, modify their states, and initiate transactions. A specialized programming language, such as Solidity or Viper, is used to create such contracts. Statements such as “if...then” are often used to execute the contracts. Read more - [Blockchain for Real World Applications - Rishabh Garg. John Wiley & Sons, Inc. US, 01-388: ISBN - 9781119903734.](#)

HYPERLEDGER

Hyperledger is a global open source collaborative effort that provides the framework, standards, guidelines, and tools needed for use in a variety of industries. It welcomes any community member with programming knowledge or interest to contribute to the development of the source code. Code can be reviewed, created, modified or distributed by any programmer in the world.

Only those entities or individuals that have an authorization certificate can check transactions on the Hyperledger network. Businesses such as private or B2B that do not want their personal information on a public blockchain can use this permissioned and limited access blockchain network – the Ethereum Hyperledger.

DECENTRALIZED APPLICATIONS

In a centralized system, application software may be placed at one or more central locations, depending on the size of the client base installed. However, in a decentralized system, smart contracts are used to enable application software to run independently on a peer-to-peer blockchain network, rather than on a single machine. A **decentralized application** (dApp) constitutes a front-end, a blockchain back-end, and middleware – the software connecting the two.

Although dApps promise to solve many of the major concerns with traditional apps, they also have a number of drawbacks, such as maintenance requirements, significant performance overheads, network congestion, etc.

IDENTITY CONCERNS

Identity is central to all human activities. A valid identity is a prerequisite for school enrollment, employment applications, operating a bank account, obtaining a passport, signing contracts or accessing the financial system [Garg, 2019]. However, more than a billion individuals, including 21 million refugees, still do not have a legal identity. This is due to hidden costs, intervention of middlemen and tedious processes.

IDENTITIES ACROSS THE WORLD

People around the world have different forms of identity, such as a passport for international travel, a driver license for driving a vehicle, a voter card for elections, a social security number for keeping records of salary or self-employment, etc. [Garg, 2020]. The history of the identification system probably begins in 1803, when Napoleon Bonaparte introduced the first identification system in the world.

The French government introduced an identity card for workers with the aim of using it as a tool to transform the unrestricted society of the French Republic into a well-organized police state so that workers could not migrate to better jobs and higher wages without the employer's permission. Napoleon's ID plan was a parable for human trafficking and slavery in Russia or

Eastern Europe, but it could not prosper due to labor shortages and the emergence of self-help organizations during the World Wars [Lyon, 1994].

By the 20th century, Germany had become a highly democratic, tolerant and liberal nation with welfare schemes, social insurance and national health services. In such a milieu, the Nazis were obsessed with the economic value of workers, withholding wages, removing strikers and disabled people. The Nazis introduced a work book to record each employee's work history, including periods of redundancy and violations of work contracts. Its veiled motive was to identify the strikers, the weak, the work-shy, the undisposed, sexually promiscuous, clandestine prostitutes and the sub-proletariat. The order was turned down only in 1941-42, when the war turned against Germany [Gotz and Roth, 2004; Black, 2012].

China extended the Nazi's workbook by adapting it into a system called the dang-an dossier, which provided for the compilation of personal records from school days. Workers could not start a new vocation until their dang-an-dossier was dispatched by the former employer. This new system was completely different from the historical system, Dang-e, which was intended to supervise the nobles.

In addition, a so-called domestic registration system existed in China prevented chinese workers from moving to a different area without permission. In the 1990s the dang-an system began to break down due to the forces arising from globalization. Foreign firms entering China did not keep dang-an records and employed rural migrants without dang-an dossier.

The contemporary era of ID cards began with World War II. In 1938, the United Kingdom passed the National Registry Act, which required all residents to have an identity card [Whitley and Hosein, 2009]. In 1940, the Vichy government of France established an ID system with Greece and Poland, which is more or less retained till date. Barring a few exceptions, hardly any country, with common law, in the world has adopted a peacetime identification system.

The adoption of ID cards in Asia was reflected in a boom after WWII. The Hong Kong government introduced an identity card in 1949 to prevent immigration from mainland China and strengthen its sovereignty. Taiwan in 1949, South Korea and Singapore in the 1960s followed the suit in pretext of economic transformation.

MODERN IDENTITIES

In the United States, a nine-digit Social Security Number (SSN) is issued to all US citizens, permanent residents and temporary residents over the age of 18. Although it was originally intended to identify individuals for social security purposes, it is now also used to track individuals for taxation purpose. In practice, it has become a de facto national identification number due to its wide range of applications, such as opening a bank account or applying for a driving license.

Social Insurance Number was introduced in Canada but ended in 2004 with the introduction of Personal Information Protection and Electronic Document as real ID numbers.

In Colombia, each person during childhood is issued a basic identification card called Tarjeta de Identidad which includes the date of birth and a small serial number. Upon reaching the age of 18, each citizen is re-issued a citizenship card (Cedula de Ciudadanía), which is essential in all public and private matters.

In Mexico, the identification number is called Clave Única de Registro de Población (CURP). Though various other IDs, such as the social security number, allotted by Instituto Mexicano del Seguro Social, and the Registro Federal del Contribuyente (RFC) assigned by the Treasury, are also in vogue but the election card, Credencial de Elector or Credencial del INE, issued by the Instituto Nacional Electoral is given the highest recognition.

A national identity card, the Documento Nacional de Identidad (DNI), is issued by the Registro Nacional de las Personas at the time of birth in Argentina, except for immigrants who receive numbers starting with 92,000,000. This ID is required to apply for credit, open a bank account and exercise the right of franchise. Since parents are required to sign-up their children, the poor, and especially orphans, are left out.

Brazil has two systems – first, the Registro Geral (RG) which is a number assigned by states and some organizations such as the armed forces as an authorized national ID. Since these are allotted at the state level, it is possible have the same RG number for two citizens in different states

The second system, the Cadastro de Pessoas Físicas (CPF), is a federal and unique one, but it was originally created for taxation purposes. In Brazil, one or both numbers are necessary for certain common tasks, such as opening a bank account or obtaining a driver's license.

Within the European Economic Area and Switzerland, the European Health Insurance Card is issued for health care purposes. This card lists a code called an identification number. In Finland, the personal identification code, henkilötunnus (HETU or Swedish – Personbeteckning) has been in vogue since 1964 and is used to identify citizens for government and corporate transactions.

In France, the INSEE code that originated during the Vichy regime is used for identification, social insurance, employment, and taxation purposes. In Germany, as of 2007 only a decentralized database was maintained by social insurance companies, which allocated a social insurance number to almost every person. After 2008 the former tax file numbers were replaced by new taxpayer identification numbers, Steuerliche Identifikationsnummer or Steuer-IdNr. Individuals who are both employee and self-employed at the same time can get two taxpayer identification numbers. The corresponding number for organizations are issued by the Federal Central Tax Office, and is named Wirtschafts-Identifikationsnummer.

In Italy, a financial code (Codicefiscale) is issued in the format SSSNNNYMDDZZZZX at the time of birth. SSS are the first three consonants in the family name (if there are not enough consonants the first vowel, then X are used); NNN is the first name, from which the first, third and fourth consonants are used; YY are the last two digits of the year of birth, M is the letter assigned to the month of birth, DD are the last two letters of birth; ZZZZ is the specific area code for the municipality where the person was born; X is a parity character which is calculated by adding together the letters in even and odd positions. The letters of the month are used alphabetically, but only the letters A to E, H, L, M, P, R to T are used (thus, January is A and October is R); To differentiate between genders, 40 is added to the day of birth for females; and for foreigners a country-wide code is used in place of a municipal code.

The Gambia and Nigeria allot 11-digit identification numbers to their citizens called National Identification Numbers [NIMC, 2022].

The national ID number in Zimbabwe is an eleven character alphanumeric code managed by the Office of the Registrar General. It has a 2-digit prefix indicating the district in which the applicant resides; the next six digits represent the applicant's unique personal code; and the last 2 digits are the prefix code of the national ID number of the original parents.

In People's Republic of China, an 18-digit ID card in the format RRRRRRRYYMMDDSSSC is mandatory for all citizens above 16 years of age. RRRRRR is a standard code for the administrative division of the county or city where the holder is born; YYYYMMDD is the date of birth of the holder; and SSS is a sequential code to differentiate people with the same date of birth and place of birth [Shaw, 1996; Perry, 1997]. The sequential code is odd for males and even for females.

Indonesia has rolled out a 16-digit RFID card with electronic signature, iris scan, ten-finger fingerprint scan and a high-resolution passport under the name of e-KTP (Electronic Kartu Tanda Penduduk) since 2012. This program has been designed on the basis of UIDAI of India.

India has been striving for decades to provide an official identity to all its citizens. So far, countless IDs have been floated and rolled back, leading to a state of flux and confusion amongst the citizens [Garg, 2017]. The limitation of existing IDs is that they serve dissimilar and limited purposes only. Further, it is not uncommon to find discrepancies in the citizen's profile among different repositories, causing confusion and error [Garg, 2018; 2019].

The idea of a biometric enabled Unique Identification Number (UID), or Aadhaar, was proposed by the Department of Information Technology, Government of India, with the aim of providing an authentic identity to every resident of India. More than one billion citizens have been roped to the scheme, on which an estimated 130 billion INR (UIDAI, 2022) has been spent so far. It is the world's largest biometric identification system that aims to provide identify to every such resident who lacks an individual identity.

Blockchain Innovations

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ONE WORLD-ONE IDENTITY

When a citizen can have the same name on different documents, why do we allot different identification numbers for different services? Can every citizen not be issued a 20 digit Universal Identification Number? Global identity will not only bring authenticity but it will also prevent a person from having citizenship of two different countries or availing benefits of their welfare schemes. This will curb innumerable crimes like infiltration, impersonation, fake passport, etc.

25 September 2021

The phenomenal progress in the field of computer and information technology during the last two and a half decades has shrunken the entire world into a mobile device. All tasks like education, banking, business, travel, transport, cinema, entertainment are being handled by this pocket-friendly apparatus.

In the times of Covid-19 when the world was confined within their households, people steered multi-billion dollar business, conducted classes, listened to lectures, and organized conferences through their laptops, and mobile phones. When one can avail all the facilities through digital platforms, why do we still count on physical ID cards whose authenticity, security and transferability is never assured?

A valid identity is a pre-requisite for any educational, commercial, financial or administrative transaction. Unfortunately 1100 million people around the world do not have any proof of identity and 400 million of these people are from the poorest sectors of the world.

To make identity universal and unique, Rishabh Garg, a sophomore of the Birla Institute of Technology and Science India, has proposed the idea of a universal ID number. He believes that just as every single citizen in every culture is given a name at the time of birth and that name is recorded in all records as his identity, similarly every citizen of the world is assigned a Universal Identification Number by a competent authority such as the United Nations. This unique identification number can be of 20 digits globally.

This identification number will not only establish the identity of the person but will also be able to count his educational achievement, financial transactions, property details, information of legal heirs, healthcare, postal address etc.

Once his date of birth is entered correctly, he will automatically be eligible to vote as and when he attains the age of 18. He can cast his vote from his mobile or laptop based on the Unique Identification Number. After the closure of the polling at the scheduled time, the result can be declared instantly. This will save billions of dollars, time, and human resources.

Similarly, if one updates his postal address periodically on the portal of the postal department, then without inscribing the address, his important mail will reach at his doorsteps on the basis of 20 digit identification number. Last month Prime Minister of India announced the enactment of Ayushman Health Card. In the coming two years, such identity cards can be implemented in other work areas as well. However, the allotment of a separate identification number for each service and its subsequent linking with the Aadhaar number would call for endless problems to a common man.

Reiterating his stand Rishabh has discussed the idea of *One World One Identity* in university circles with more than 80,000 scholars on LinkedIn. According to him, *One World One Identity* would help in improved educational, banking, investment, healthcare, and other services, where a single card with unique number shall hold all the substantive data of a citizen, whether it be personal, biometric, educational, professional, medical, legal or financial, in different siloes, in a duly encrypted manner.

Unique digital ID for citizen health and care facilities

Records will be protected, step to help poor and middle class: PM at launch

NEW DELHI, SEPTEMBER 22

ALMOST a year after it was implemented on pilot basis in six Union Territories, Prime Minister Narendra Modi launched the Ayushman Bharat Digital Mission for the entire country Monday. It involves creation of not just a unique health ID for every citizen, but also creation of digital healthcare professionals and facilities registry.

The Prime Minister said the digital initiative has the "potential of bringing a revolutionary change in India's healthcare facilities. Today, we will enter a new phase in our campaign to strengthen health facilities. Today, a mission is being started which has huge power to revolutionise the health facilities of India. This mission will play a big role in overcoming problems faced by the poor and middle class in the country in accessing treatment".

He underlined that through the initiative – it will enable individuals to discover hospitals, laboratories and pharmacies across the country – the health record of every citizen will be protected, step to help poor and middle class: PM at launch

Continued on page 6

Unique health ID: Modi launches Ayushman Bharat Digital Mission

DPS BOY SHINES AT INDIAN INTERNATIONAL SCIENCE FESTIVAL

Rishabh Garg, a student of Delhi Public School, Bhopal was invited for the 2nd Indian International Science Festival, 2016. The Ministry of Science & Technology, Ministry of Earth Science (Govt. of India) and Advanced Materials & Process Research Institute, Bhopal selected him to represent Madhya Pradesh, Chhattargarh and Odisha in ISF 2016. In an outreach programme conducted by AMPRI, Bhopal was honoured by the National Convener Secretary of ISF

भोपाल के ऋषभ ने तीन साल पहले दिया था बहुउद्देशीय कार्ड का आइडिया

भारत के अर्थव्यवस्था की वृद्धि बढ़ावे के लिये की सरकार

भोपाल के ऋषभ ने तीन साल पहले दिया था बहुउद्देशीय कार्ड का आइडिया

Modi launches digital Ayushman health IDs

ऋषभ ने बनाया जैनात्मिक इनफोमेशन टैकर

भोपाल के ऋषभ ने तीन साल पहले दिया था बहुउद्देशीय कार्ड का आइडिया

डीपीएस के ऋषभ गर्ग को मिला सीएसआईआर इनोवेशन अवॉर्ड

प्रेस नोट में देरी की सरकार, विज्ञान-2020 को छानने में ऋषभ प्रोफेसर ली की वरदान

and a mobile SIM with unique digital identification number, generic data and biometric information of the subject. This digital number would serve as the digital identity of a person and all information right from registration of birth, school admission, grade sheets of all examinations, certificates, credentials, degrees, achievements, awards, scholarships, job details, income, assets, liabilities, vehicles, marital, medical and legal history) are recorded in the same card. During the Platinum Jubilee Celebration of CSIR at Vigyan Bhawan in New Delhi, Rishabh's project was applauded by prime minister Narendra Modi.

One World - One Identity

Rishabh Garg | BITS India

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He has authored a book on **Blockchain for Real World Applications** (*John Wiley & Sons Inc. US*) and another on **Self Sovereign Identities** that was published in six international languages at Germany, France, Italy, Moldova, Spain, and Portugal. He is a Journal Referee with IEEE Internet of Things, and a Program Committee Member cum Reviewer for International Conferences organized by AIRCC at Toronto (Canada), Youngs (Australia), and London (UK).

Rishabh is a recipient of the National Award for Exceptional Achievements in Innovation from the **President of India** and National CSIR Innovation Award from the **Prime Minister of India**.

Garg [2016 - 2023] introduced the idea of **One World - One Identity**, which is a lone alternative to multiple identity cards. This globally unique multipurpose digital identity number can be operated with the help of state-of-the-art blockchain technology.

Each person living on Earth can be assigned a 20-digit identity on a specific date. This will enable individuals to store their login credentials and personally identifiable information in a wallet or application known as IPFS [**Garg, 2021**]. For file sharing, IPFS will use a decentralized, distributed peer-to-peer (P2P) network model that can be spread across multiple computers or nodes. Files can be divided into segments and kept in a network of nodes that keep track of them using their hash. The original file can be reconstructed when the entire file is put together, based on the hash value of each component.

In contrast to the traditional Hyper-Text Transfer Protocol (HTTP) families of protocols or centralized namespaces, IPFS is a location-based storage system. When a storage system is location-based, it keeps track of hosts using an IP address or other logical addressing scheme mapped to a familiar name. If the host changes its name or address, the name service table needs to be updated as well.

A content identifier is required in content-based addressing storage to pinpoint the precise location of the file. Instead of a logical address, here the data is accessed based on its cryptographic hash, which acts as a digital file fingerprint. The network always returns the same content based on the hash, regardless of who and where the file is uploaded. IPFS is a decentralized way of storing files, whereby, for identity management, the original document can be saved on IPFS, while the metadata or hash of its contents can be stored on a blockchain server.

An additional layer of security can also be added by biometric solutions, such as thumb impression on a smartphone, fingerprint, hand geometry, voice or facial recognition, thermal mapping, eye patterns – retinal scan, iris scan or any other biometric verification protocol. Biometric data can be saved and processed using a database server, physical tokens, encrypted tokens or both. Secure systems often store biometric templates on-device or on-premises to enable identity verification without transmitting any sensitive biometric data to another server or location on the Internet.

Although the internal mechanism for biometric authentication relies on technology, it is remarkably simple and quick from the user's point of view. It's easier to put your finger on a scanner than to type in a long password with several special characters to instantly unlock an account. Most biometric authentication methods are only used with physical applications; you may not transfer or communicate biological metrics online. Biometrics such as fingerprints, iris scans, facial patterns and others are difficult to reconstruct with current technology. The chance of your fingerprint matching someone else's is one in 64 billion. Read more - [Blockchain for Real World Applications - Rishabh Garg, John Wiley & Sons, Inc. US, 01-388: ISBN - 9781119903734](#).

Recently, it has been discovered that by using blockchain, the traditional building blocks of any deep learning model can be converted into a secure system. It is a biometric recognition architecture that uses blockchain technology to provide fault tolerant access in a distributed environment. It protects both the deep learning model and the biometric template and alerts the entire system when a specific component is tampered with. It also makes it easier to identify any potential disruptions.

Biometric identification systems, which combine biometrics and blockchain technology, can be used to improve security, reach consensus in volatile environments, and make auditable decisions. Through a personal device such as a smartphone, users can share their digital ID with the service provider even if they are not physically present and still be able to access essential services without jeopardizing their privacy.

Without the user's explicit permission, no transaction will take place through their information. By allowing the user to manage their personally identifiable information, the system will be more interoperable, the user will be free to access the data across multiple platforms and not be forced to use only one.

Since there are no geographic restrictions on the use of blockchain identities, users can access and verify their identities from any corner of the world. Blockchain will eliminate the need for multiple usernames and passwords by enabling users to enjoy a self-sovereign and encrypted digital identity.

A card with a unique number shall store all physical data of a citizen, whether personal, biometric, educational, extra-curricular, vocational, medical, legal or financial, in separate silos, in a fully encrypted manner. In this way **One World – One Identity** will prove to be effective in

better education, banking, investment, healthcare, public distribution schemes and other services [Garg 2017].

ENCRYPTION

Encryption of communication enables only the true sender and intended receiver of the message to read the relevant content. There are three main categories of cryptography – asymmetric key cryptography, hash function cryptography, and symmetric key cryptography.

There have been several turning points in the history of cryptography that laid the foundation of contemporary algorithms. The term “cipher” originally referred to a general idea for transmitting secret messages that included letters as a fundamental component. Simple substitution cipher, Caesar cipher, Hill cipher, Playfair cipher, Vigenere cipher, transposition cipher, etc. are some of the known examples. Playfair cipher in C can securely transfer between its source and destination without leaking information using encryption-decryption.

The Hill cipher is a polygraphic substitution cipher based on linear algebra that was founded by Lester S. Hill in 1929. It can easily form a coherent cipher when used with digraphs (two-letter blocks), trigraphs (three-letter blocks), or any other multiple-sized blocks. Many more cryptographic algorithms can also be implemented, including the RSA algorithm, the Multiple Precision Arithmetic Library, the GNU Multiple Precision Arithmetic Library, the Chinese Remainder Theorem, and the SHA-512 hash in Java. Read more - [Blockchain for Real World Applications - Rishabh Garg. John Wiley & Sons, Inc. US, 01-388: ISBN - 9781119903734.](#)

CYBERSECURITY

Cyber security protects systems and networks from online threats. The cyber-attack landscape has expanded rapidly in recent years. Attackers use malware such as Trojans, rootkits and viruses which are known as Distributed Denial of Service (DDoS) attacks, Man in the Middle (MITM) attacks, Phishing attacks, and Ransomware attacks. Businesses around the world have embraced blockchain, which has emerged as a potential cybersecurity mitigation tool.

EDUCATION AND EMPLOYMENT

Millions of applicants across the world submit their academic credentials every year hoping to be recruited by higher education institutions or hired by corporate houses. A large number of applicants exaggerate their educational background during each recruitment.

In order to preserve the authenticity of document, a credential holder can keep all of their credentials in their Pi wallet and share it with validators in an encrypted mode using the Ethereum blockchain. In compliance with Garg [2021b] the hash generated after uploading the credentials to IPFS can have two layers of encryption. The student’s public key may be used to create the first layer of encryption, and then the issuer’s private key may be used to implement the second and third layers of encryption (authorization). It will be decrypted using the issuer’s

public key to verify the shared credential. The encrypted hash produced may be compared with the one stored in the issuer's database. If both match then the credential may be considered valid.

Often a student's certificate of achievement does not mention the curriculum or methods of instruction. It prevents a student from transferring his/her academic credit or learning achievements from one institution to another. A complete record of curriculum, teaching, learning and assessment can be maintained by giving each student access to an assessment dashboard [Garg, 2021]. Employers will be able to select the best candidate, examine their past and evaluate supporting documents provided a candidate's achievements are recorded at each stage of his/her academic career on a robust platform such as Blockchain. As such, blockchain can prove to be a useful tool for conducting background checks of a candidate, and save time, money and human resources. Read more - [Blockchain for Real World Applications - Rishabh Garg. John Wiley & Sons, Inc. US, 01-388: ISBN - 9781119903734.](#)

HEALTHCARE

Healthcare institutions around the world are grappling with issues such as delays in data breaches, origination of medical supplies, and chargeback claims for prescription drugs. Blockchain offers a wide range of applications and benefits in healthcare. It helps manage drug supply chains, protect the transmission of patient medical records, and provide health researchers with access to biological and genetic codes.

Using blockchain, all patient medical information, including prescriptions, notes and lab results, can be available in a single view. Each piece of information can be converted into a separate hash function. Each hash function is distinct and can only be shared with the permission of the owner of the data. Additionally, using blockchain, it is possible to monitor an item from the point of its manufacture through each stage of the supply chain, giving the buyer complete visibility and transparency over the products he is about to purchase. The use of technology can speed up claim settlements for business partners and insurance companies, enable law enforcement to investigate any suspicious activity like drug trafficking or hoarding during major emergencies like pandemics, and connect organ donors, organ recipients, and healthcare facilities to facilitate organ transplantation.

GENOMICS

An infinite number of genetic data points can be stored securely on a blockchain. It is turning into a market where individuals can trade their genetic data. It tends to create comprehensive databases and provide vital information to scientists more quickly than ever before. Unlike current systems, if the data owners can establish contact with the data buyers directly without the use of a middleman business, the analysis cost can be reduced and the data owners can be able to make more profit. Read more - [Blockchain for Real World Applications - Rishabh Garg. John Wiley & Sons, Inc. US, 01-388: ISBN - 9781119903734.](#)

SUPPLY CHAIN

Every day, billions of consumer goods are produced and distributed through complex supply chains that reach every corner of the world. However, information about the origin, production and use of these commodities throughout their life cycle remains obscure. Each product passes through an extensive network of suppliers, traders, distributors, transporters, warehouses and other facilities before being sold to the end customer, but they almost always remain a mystery throughout this complex journey.

As a result, a critical business barrier that prevents most organizations from knowing anything about their second and third tier suppliers is supply chain visibility. Transparency and visibility across various channels of the entire supply chain can ease the movement of goods from raw materials to finished goods manufacturing, testing and distribution.

Better results can be expected from the application of blockchain technology in the supply chain. The supply chain can use a shared, consensus-based public ledger to trace the processes of origin and manufacture of products. In supply chain management, the lifecycle, certification and documentation of a product can be made instantly available to all parties through blockchain. From manufacturer to storage, travel, distribution and sale, products can be tracked.

FOOD SUPPLY

A large proportion of the food we consume is produced through a convoluted global supply chain, which also increases the risk of adulteration, tampering, misrepresentation and purposeful substitution. The global food sector loses billions of dollars every year from food theft. Milk, tea, coffee, fruit juice, olive oil, maple syrup, shellfish, honey and many other foods are included in most food categories. The average person cannot imagine his day without these foods.

As the global supply chain expands, food safety is becoming a major concern for both consumers and regulators. According to the World Health Organization, one in ten people are affected by food poisoning, resulting in 33 million years of healthy life and 420,000 deaths every year [WHO Report, 2019]. Additionally, foodborne illness claims the lives of 125,000 children under the age of five every year. Here too blockchain is a reliable alternative that can preserve the traceability of immutable documents. Using blockchain, it is possible to monitor food products at all levels, from the farm to the superstores.

Blockchain is also rapidly establishing its dominance in industries other than food supply chain management. Although the majority of the top businesses have cutting-edge digital infrastructure, including supply chain management (SCM) and enterprise resource planning (ERP) software, the system still exhibits analogue gaps when products are tracked from connected manufacturing equipment (origin) to digital shipping notices and RFID scanning. Even the most advanced machinery cannot accurately calculate how long a product will last. Companies can use blockchain technology to maintain a real-time, immutable digital ledger of

all transactions and movements for each member of their supply chain network. Read more - [Blockchain for Real World Applications - Rishabh Garg. John Wiley & Sons, Inc. US, 01-388: ISBN - 9781119903734.](#)

REAL ESTATE

Since time immemorial, real estate has been a reliable investment option for the wealthy. Only a small number of assets provide the same amount of capital growth. Despite all this, there are many constraints on a global landscape, such as access to potential sponsors, financiers and fund managers; citizenship of the country; recognition of buyer's business establishment, international bank accounts, credit scores, matching funds, etc. In addition, each property owner needlessly spends an enormous amount of money registering title, releasing liens, and transferring ownership to municipal records to secure their investments.

Blockchain offers all players the same version of the truth about the title of land ownership. As a result, procedures that are often associated with real estate, such as double-selling, fake registries and encroachments, can be eliminated. Smart contracts can be used to regulate real estate transactions, while cutting down on paperwork, middlemen, and real estate appraisers.

ELECTORAL PROCESS

The primary goal of any election authority is to conduct elections in a fair, reliable and transparent manner. To achieve this goal, the bureaucracy recklessly spends billions of dollars and throws millions of government employees into electoral duty. Blockchain technology can be effective in making the voting process simple, smooth and transparent.

This can help people to vote who often fail to exercise their right to franchise, perhaps because they live in remote areas, lack access to polling places, or are utterly incapacitated. Because it uses a distributed ledger, voters can cast their ballots from anywhere in the world without sacrificing privacy. It makes it easy for voters to cast their votes on Election Day sitting at home, without standing in line or going through excessive formalities.

When every citizen has a decentralized identity, also known as a self-sovereign identity, a distributed ledger can be used to record all the important events in their lives. Citizens may be allowed to participate in the election process based on their information, including their usual place of residence (the constituency where they are eligible to vote), date of birth (when they reach legal voting age), and subject to other conditions (if any). A voter can cast his vote through his login ID but cannot again use the same decentralized identification number on the basis of which he has cast his vote during the said election. By segregating the votes of each constituency using software on the second day of polling, the blockchain will tally the votes cast in favor of each candidate through different nodes.

Nevertheless, it is a secret that every citizen knows that many hostile and illegal activities surround the voting process and election results. Nowhere in the world is the election process complete without booth capturing, replacement of voting equipment at polling places or false

voting claims. Governments may be wary of implementing blockchain-based elections because they are fully auditable processes that limit the possibilities of manipulation for political parties. Read more - [Blockchain for Real World Applications - Rishabh Garg. John Wiley & Sons, Inc. US, 01-388: ISBN - 9781119903734.](#)

BANKING & FINANCE

The purpose of the creation of banking institutions was probably to enable all kinds of trade and business by bringing people together. Blockchain makes it easy for remote untrusted parties in the banking and financial sectors to reach a consensus on the state of the database, without the help of gatekeepers. Users will be able to choose who and how much they want to share their identity with. On the blockchain, they only need to enter their identity once. If the service providers are blockchain-powered, there is no need for any user to repeat their registration.

Similar to a trusted bookkeeper, it manages all financial transactions including payments, settlement systems, fundraising, securities management, loans, credits and trade finance. In terms of identity verification, payments, withdrawals, settlements, credits and loans, asset transfers, peer-to-peer transfers, hedge funds, security and accountability, it has been able to outperform traditional systems.

This can dramatically reduce transaction fees, by reducing the overhead expenses that incur when manually setting up, executing, and exchanging assets. The elimination of intermediaries has made processes, such as cross-border payments, trade and settlements faster, more reliable and less expensive.

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TRADE FINANCE

The transfer of information, the transfer of assets, and the process of making payments all rely significantly on paper-based business operations in trade finance. These contracts may be better explained in the Python programming language rather than legal so that traders can understand

them. Therefore, blockchain and smart contracts provide business investors with a secure, open, transparent, auditable and automated transaction environment. It has the potential to transform trade finance by streamlining the operations of smart contracts, corporate resource planning, lightning network, pre- and post-trade processes, accounts and audits, loyalty programs, etc.

DECENTRALIZED FINANCE

Decentralized finance (DeFi) is an emerging financial technology built on blockchain. It is quite different from other financial networks as it is open and programmable. Smart contracts and the terms that underpin them enable it to operate automatically without a central authority. It allows developers to create new payment, investment, lending, trade and exchange models independent of banks and other institutions.

In centralized finance, the bank, financial institution, or business that guarantees the transaction owns your money. They take a huge dividend from your money as they have a lot of financial freedom. In DeFi, a smart contract acts as a transaction substitute for a financial institution. Once they go live, only smart contracts comply. These contracts cannot be modified because they are always designed for automation.

Decentralized financial protocols have given consumers around the world access to a wide range of new economic opportunities. Asset management, tokenization, token derivatives, decentralized autonomy, data analysis and valuation, payments, lending and lending, insurance, margin trading, markets, gaming and yield farming are all covered. Read more - [Blockchain for Real World Applications - Rishabh Garg, John Wiley & Sons, Inc. US, 01-388: ISBN - 9781119903734](#).

ETHEREUM AS A DEFI PLATFORM

Ethereum is an innovative, algorithm-driven economic system fueled by trust, opportunity, and financial access. It can be leveraged in sending money, using programmable currency, lending or borrowing money, participating in no-loss lotteries, trading tokens, quadratic trading, fund raising, crowdfunding, portfolio management, etc. Besides, prediction markets can also benefit from Ethereum blockchain in several ways – increased access, resistance to censorship, and the removal of intermediaries.

DISTRIBUTED RESOURCES AND IOT

Blockchain provides more secure data storage and management with substantial benefits, by offering a uniform, interoperable and tamper-proof architecture for governments, businesses, consumers and IoT management systems. It performs middle and back office functions the same way the Internet and web front perform them, automates tasks to increase productivity and opens up new business possibilities.

Connecting IoT systems to blockchain assures the efficiency and data security of IoT applications. An algorithm can be combined with a new leader selection technique to make it easier to use blockchain on IoT end devices with restricted resource availability. IoT data held on

a shared blockchain ledger makes it possible for all parties to track the origin of components throughout a product's lifecycle. It is now safe, simple and economical to share all relevant information with regulatory bodies, shippers and manufacturers. Read more - [Blockchain for Real World Applications - Rishabh Garg, John Wiley & Sons, Inc. US, 01-388: ISBN - 9781119903734](#).

E-GOVERNANCE

Despite the fact that many geeks have attempted to address security issues in e-governance systems, security requirements are generally not met by existing frameworks and models. Since it is impossible to ignore the lack of trust in Internet-mediated transactions and unauthorized access by insiders to the system, the deployment of blockchain technology seems to be the only way to address these shortcomings. This promises a more effective, safe and a secure public service.

Hundreds of blockchain initiatives have been launched in more than thirty countries over the past four to five years to replace government systems. Estonia has adopted a blockchain-enabled ID to verify the identity of citizens. Blockchain technology is being used to build electronic voting systems in Australia and Ukraine. In the US, it is being used to securely share medical data and in the UK to enhance public services. In Georgia and Honduras, land registration is being managed using distributed ledger technology. In the near future, China dreams of building a blockchain city.

Automated blockchain systems can enable government agencies to operate more effectively, by reducing the effort, time and expense usually required to manually manage access to their networks. In addition, it can also facilitate:

- maintaining the details of the issuing and verifying authority;
- securing documents from tampering;
- making all relevant information available to the authorities through the public key;
- access to personal information or original documents anytime, anywhere through users' private keys;
- reducing fraud, tax evasion and malpractice; and
- boosting the country's economy [Garg, 2020].

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DECENTRALIZED STREAMING

Videos can be entertaining, instructive and empowering. However, broadcasters uploading video to the Internet have to transcode it first. It consumes up to 80% of the entire Internet bandwidth, making video streaming very expensive. Video infrastructure is needed to provide more scalable and cost-effective solutions and to meet this, technologies such as blockchain can allow app

developers in the video transcoding market access to a wider range of distributed processors, which are accessible, safe and cost effective.

DUAL MINING

Dual mining is the practice of performing different operations on the same gear. The phrase first appeared in the context of PoW mining, where it described the concurrent mining of multiple cryptocurrencies using a single GPU to run the PoW hashing algorithm. Dual mining-using a GPU to mine cryptocurrencies like Ethereum, as well as using it to transcode video as a video miner on your own network-may still be possible for video streaming. One advantage of employing transcoding as an additional activity to dual mining is that it uses fewer GPU cores than other possible workloads because the GPU's hardware encoders and decoders do most of the work.

EVER-EXPANDING NETWORK

The ever-expanding blockchain network covers many aspects of the real world, including human resource management, law enforcement, public assistance, welfare delivery, postal services, bills and payments, taxation, drugs, vaccination and community health, mediclaim settlement, insurance, shipping, freight, public transport, travel and mobility, ride-hailing, air travel, Internet of Things, information and communication, messaging, hospitality, entertainment, gambling, food and beverage, fisheries, animal husbandry, agriculture and natural resources, infrastructure and energy, production, real estate, construction, vehicles, wills and inheritances.

IN A NUTSHELL

Blockchain does not promise to make user a billionaire overnight or offer a mechanism to protect their financial transactions from politically inspired governments. What is demonstrably true, however, is that it offers a new approach to structuring administrative and economic organizations, while significantly reducing the cost of trust through a radical, decentralized ledger approach.

Read more - [Blockchain for Real World Applications - Rishabh Garg. John Wiley & Sons, Inc. US, 01-388: ISBN - 9781119903734.](#)

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